

Impact of Linear Homogeneous Recurrent Relation Analysis

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For a first order recursion $x_{n+1}=f(x_n)$, one just needs to start with an initial value x_0 and can generate all remaining terms using the recurrence relation. For a second order recursion $x_{n+1}=f(x_n, x_{n-1})$, one needs to begin with two values x_0 and x_1 . Higher order recurrence relations require correspondingly more initial values.

A linear **homogeneous** recurrence of order k is expressed this way: $A_0a_n + A_1a_{n-1} + A_2a_{n-2} + \dots + A_{k-1}a_{n-k} = 0$

2. Objectives

The aim of this paper is to solve the linear recurrence relation

$$x_{n+1} = a_0x_n + a_1x_{n-1} + \dots + a_{n-1}x_1 + a_nx_0, n = 0, 1, 2, \dots,$$

when its constant coefficients are in arithmetic, respective geometric progression. Rather surprising, when the coefficients are in arithmetic progression, the solution is a sequence of certain generalized Fibonacci numbers, but not of usual Fibonacci numbers, while if they are in geometric progression the solution is again a geometric progression, with different ratio. Recurrence relations can be divided into two: Linear and Non-Linear. Linear homogeneous recurrence relations with constant coefficients; Solving linear homogeneous recurrence relations with constant coefficients; Solving linear homogeneous recurrence relations with constant coefficients of degree two and degree three; Generating functions; Using generating functions to solve recurrence relations. Some recurrence relations are solvable using algebraic techniques, but they're often tricky,

ABSTRACT

A linear homogeneous recurrence relation of degree k with constant coefficients is a recurrence. A recurrence relation is an equation that recursively defines a sequence or multidimensional array of values, once one or more initial terms are given; each further term of the sequence or array is defined as a function of the preceding terms.

1. INTRODUCTION

A recurrence relation is an equation that defines a sequence based on a rule that gives the next term as a function of the previous term(s). The simplest form of a recurrence relation is the case where the next term depends only on the immediately previous term. If we denote the n th term in the sequence by x_n , such a recurrence relation is of the form $x_{n+1}=f(x_n)$ for some function f . One such example is $x_{n+1}=2-x_n/2$. A recurrence relation can also be higher order, where the term x_{n+1} could depend not only on the previous term x_n but also on earlier terms such as x_{n-1} , x_{n-2} , etc. A second order recurrence relation depends just on x_n and x_{n-1} and is of the form $x_{n+1}=f(x_n, x_{n-1})$ for some function f with two inputs. For example, the recurrence relation $x_{n+1}=x_n+x_{n-1}$ can generate the Fibonacci numbers. To generate sequence based on a recurrence relation, one must start with some initial values.

they require some math many of you don't know, and it still won't work for many relations.

3. Methodology

Linear Homogeneous Recurrence Relations Definition: A linear homogeneous recurrence relation of degree k with constant coefficients is a recurrence relation of the form $a_n = c_1 a_{n-1} + c_2 a_{n-2} + \dots + c_k a_{n-k}$, where c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k are real numbers, and $c_k \neq 0$ it is linear because the right-hand side is a sum of the previous terms of the sequence each multiplied by a function of n . it is homogeneous because no terms occur that are not multiples of the a_j s. Each coefficient is a constant. The degree is k because a_n is expressed in terms of the previous k terms of the sequence. By strong induction, a sequence satisfying such a recurrence relation is uniquely determined by the recurrence relation and the k initial conditions $a_0 = C_0, a_1 = C_1, \dots, a_{k-1} = C_{k-1}$. Examples of Linear Homogeneous Recurrence Relations $P_n = (1.11) P_{n-1}$ linear homogeneous recurrence relation of degree one $f_n = f_{n-1} + f_{n-2}$ linear homogeneous recurrence relation of degree two not linear $H_n = 2 H_{n-1} + 1$ not homogeneous $B_n = n B_{n-1}$ coefficients are not constants. Solving Linear Homogeneous Recurrence Relations The basic approach is to look for solutions of the form $a_n = r^n$, where r is a constant. Note that $a_n = r^n$ is a solution to the recurrence relation $a_n = c_1 a_{n-1} + c_2 a_{n-2} + \dots + c_k a_{n-k}$ if and only if $r^n = c_1 r^{n-1} + c_2 r^{n-2} + \dots + c_k r^{n-k}$. Algebraic manipulation yields the characteristic equation: $r^k - c_1 r^{k-1} - c_2 r^{k-2} - \dots - c_k = 0$ The sequence $\{a_n\}$ with $a_n = r^n$ is a solution if and only if r is a solution to the characteristic equation. The solutions to the characteristic equation are called the characteristic roots of the recurrence relation. The roots are used to give an explicit

formula for all the solutions of the recurrence relation. Solving Linear Homogeneous Recurrence Relations of Degree Two:

Theorem 1: Let c_1 and c_2 be real numbers. Suppose that $r^2 - c_1 r - c_2 = 0$ has two distinct roots r_1 and r_2 . Then the sequence $\{a_n\}$ is a solution to the recurrence relation $a_n = c_1 a_{n-1} + c_2 a_{n-2}$ if and only if for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, where α_1 and α_2 are constants.

Example: What is the solution to the recurrence relation $a_n = a_{n-1} + 2a_{n-2}$ with $a_0 = 2$ and $a_1 = 7$? Solution: The characteristic equation is $r^2 - r - 2 = 0$. Its roots are $r = 2$ and $r = -1$. Therefore, $\{a_n\}$ is a solution to the recurrence relation if and only if $a_n = \alpha_1 2^n + \alpha_2 (-1)^n$, for some constants α_1 and α_2 . To find the constants α_1 and α_2 , note that $a_0 = 2 = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2$ and $a_1 = 7 = \alpha_1 2 + \alpha_2 (-1)$. Solving these equations, we find that $\alpha_1 = 3$ and $\alpha_2 = -1$. Hence, the solution is the sequence $\{a_n\}$ with $a_n = 3 \cdot 2^n - (-1)^n$. To find an explicit formula for the Fibonacci numbers: The sequence of Fibonacci numbers satisfies the recurrence relation $f_n = f_{n-1} + f_{n-2}$ with the initial conditions: $f_0 = 0$ and $f_1 = 1$. Solution: The roots of the characteristic equation $r^2 - r - 1 = 0$. For some constants α_1 and α_2 : Using the initial conditions $f_0 = 0$ and $f_1 = 1$, we have Solving, we obtain.

Theorem 2 : Let c_1 and c_2 be real numbers with $c_2 \neq 0$. Suppose that $r^2 - c_1 r - c_2 = 0$ has one repeated root r_0 . Then the sequence $\{a_n\}$ is a solution to the recurrence relation $a_n = c_1 a_{n-1} + c_2 a_{n-2}$ if and only if for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, where α_1 and α_2 are constants.

Example: What is the solution to the recurrence relation $a_n = 6a_{n-1} - 9a_{n-2}$ with $a_0 = 1$ and $a_1 = 6$? Solution: The characteristic equation is $r^2 - 6r + 9 = 0$. The only root is $r = 3$. Therefore, $\{a_n\}$ is a solution to the recurrence relation if and only if $a_n = \alpha_1 3^n + \alpha_2 n(3)^n$ where α_1 and α_2 are constants. To find the constants α_1 and α_2 , note that $a_0 = 1 = \alpha_1$ and $a_1 = 6 = \alpha_1 \cdot 3 + \alpha_2 \cdot 3$. Solving, we find that $\alpha_1 = 1$ and $\alpha_2 = 1$. Hence, $a_n = 3^n + n \cdot 3^n$.

Solving Linear Homogeneous Recurrence Relations of Arbitrary Degree This theorem can be used to solve linear homogeneous recurrence relations with constant coefficients of any degree when the characteristic equation has distinct roots. Theorem 3 : Let c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k be real numbers. Suppose that the characteristic equation $r^k - c_1 r^{k-1} - \dots - c_k = 0$ has k distinct roots r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k . Then a sequence $\{a_n\}$ is a solution of the recurrence relation $a_n = c_1 a_{n-1} + c_2 a_{n-2} + \dots + c_k a_{n-k}$ if and only if for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, where $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_k$ are constants.

4. Method and Solution

$$U_n = C_1 U_{n-1} + C_2 U_{n-2} + \dots + C_d U_{n-d}$$

Where C_1, C_2, \dots, C_d are number and $C_d \neq 0$.

$$P_n = U_n + U' \text{ and } q_n = \beta U_n$$

$$P_n = (C_1 U_{n-1} + C_2 U_{n-2} + \dots + C_d U_{n-d}) + (C_n U'_n + C_2 U'_{n-2} + \dots + C_d U'_{n-d})$$

$$= C_1 (U_{n-1} + U'_{n-1}) + C_2 (U_{n-2} + U'_{n-2}) + \dots + C_d (U_{n-d} + U'_{n-d})$$

$$= C_1 P_{n-1} + C_2 P_{n-2} + \dots + C_d P_{n-d}$$

So, P_n is a solution of the recurrence.

$$q_n = \beta U_n$$

$$= \beta (C_1 U_{n-1} + C_2 U_{n-2} + \dots + C_d U_{n-d})$$

$$= C_1 (\beta U_{n-1}) + C_2 (\beta U_{n-2}) + \dots + C_d (\beta U_{n-d})$$

$$= C_1 q_{n-1} + C_2 q_{n-2} + \dots + C_d q_{n-d}$$

So, q_n is a solution of recurrence.

Example: What is the solution of recurrence relation.

$$U_n = 2U_{n-1} + U_{n-2} - 2U_{n-3}, U_0=3, U_1=6, U_2=0$$

The Characteristic equation is

$$x^n - 2x^{n-1} - x^{n-2} + 2x^{n-3} = 0$$

$$x^3 - 2x^2 - x + 2 = 0$$

$$x_1 = -1, x_2 = 2, x_3 = 1$$

The general solution is $U_n = \beta_1 x_1^n + \beta_2 x_2^n + \beta_3 x_3^n$

$$U_n = \beta_1 (-1)^n + \beta_2 2^n + \beta_3 1^n$$

$$U_0 = 3 \implies \beta_1 + \beta_2 + \beta_3 = 3$$

$$U_1 = 6 \implies -\beta_1 + 2\beta_2 + \beta_3 = 6$$

$$U_2 = 0 \implies \beta_1 + 4\beta_2 + \beta_3 = 0$$

$$\beta_1 = -2, \beta_2 = -1, \beta_3 = 6$$

The solution is $U_n = (-2)(-1)^n + (-1)2^n + 6$

5. Conclusion

A simple and efficient method for solving linear homogeneous recursive relations has been introduced, which mainly involves synthetic divisions. This method has the advantage that it does not need to use generating function techniques or solve a system of linear equations to determine the unknown coefficients of the solution. A variety of techniques is available for finding explicit formulas for special classes of recursively defined sequences. The method explained here works for the Fibonacci and other similarly defined sequences.

Reference

- [1] <https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/246221/what-are-linear-homogeneous-and-non-homogeneous-recurrence-relations>
- [2] https://mathinsight.org/definition/recurrence_relation
- [3] Mircea I. Cîrnu. "Linear recurrence relations with the coefficients in progression"; *Annales Mathematicae et Informaticae*; 42 (2013) pp. 119-127; <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260424849>
- [4] Yiu-Kwong Man. "Solving Linear Homogeneous Recurrence Relation via the Inverse of Vander monde Matrix"; *Proceedings of the International Multi Conference of Engineers and Computer Scientists 2018 Vol I IMECS 2018, March 14-16, 2018, Hong Kong*
- [5] A. G. Shannon, R. P. Loh, R. S. Melham, A. F. Horadam "A Search for Solutions of a Functional Equation" https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-94-009-0223-7_36
- [6] <https://www.usna.edu/Users/cs/crabbe/2004-01/SI262/recur/recur.pdf>